

**Least Cost Electrification Study for Pakistan
-Pilot Study for Sindh-
using OnSSET**

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ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS

CER	Central Electrification Registry
CCG	Climate Compatible Growth
DISCOs	Distribution Companies
GIS	Geographic Information System
HV	High Voltage
ICTP	International Center for Theoretical Physics
LV	Low Voltage
MV	Medium Voltage
NEPRA	National Electric Power Regulatory Authority
OnSSET	Open-Source Spatial Electrification Tool
PPMC	Power Planning and Monitoring Company
PV	Photovoltaic
RE	Renewable Energy
SHS	Solar Home Systems
SDG 7	Sustainable Development Goal 7 (Energy Access)

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Pakistan has achieved significant expansion in generation capacity but continues to face spatial disparities in electricity access. With an electrification rate of 87.3% (81.2% grid, 6.1% off-grid) and a population of approximately 241 million, the remaining unelectrified population resides largely in remote and low-density settlements. At the same time, Pakistan operates with installed capacity of ~58 GW, peak demand of only 25–27 GW, and 5–7 GW surplus grid capacity, indicating that the electrification challenge is no longer supply-driven but planning-driven. This study applies the OpenSource Spatial Electrification Tool (OnSSET) to evaluate least-cost electrification pathways toward universal access by 2030. Results show that a hybrid strategy combining grid densification, targeted grid extension, and off-grid technologies (SHS) provides the most economically efficient pathway. The study emphasizes the importance of integrating OnSSET with Pakistan’s Central Electrification Registry (CER) as a decision-support system

This report presents results from least-cost electrification modelling of Pakistan using OnSSET under the EMP-A framework. The analysis supports Pakistan’s pathway toward universal electricity access by 2030 through spatial planning and technology optimization.

Pakistan has:

- **Population:** ~241 million
- **Electricity access: 87.3%**
 - Grid: **81.2%**
 - Off-grid: **6.1%**

Despite high national generation capacity (39,044 MW installed) and surplus grid capacity of 5,000–7,000 MW, electricity access remains uneven, especially in remote and low-density areas.

The study highlights that:

- Grid extension alone is not the most cost-effective pathway everywhere.
- A combined grid + off-grid strategy is required.
- OnSSET should serve as a decision-support layer integrated with Pakistan’s Central Electrification Registry (CER) and planning systems

2. INTRODUCTION

2.1. Power Sector of Pakistan:

The governance of Pakistan’s power sector is anchored in the NEPRA Act, 1997, as amended from time to time, which provides the legal foundation for independent regulation of electricity generation, transmission, and distribution. Sectoral direction is guided by the National Electricity Policy (NE-Policy) and the National Electricity Plan 2023-27 (NE-Plan), which together define the long-term vision, reform agenda, and for sustainable development pathway for the power sector. These instruments collectively aim to ensure affordability, reliability, sustainability, and financial viability of electricity supply while clearly delineating policy, regulatory, and operational roles across institutions.

Ministry of Energy (Power Division): Responsible for policy formulation, strategic oversight, and implementation of the NE-Policy and NE-Plan. The Ministry sets sector priorities, approves development plans, and oversees public sector power entities.

Power Planning and Monitoring Company (PPMC): Functions as the technical arm of Ministry, responsible for policy and strategic planning, strategic oversight of integrated generation, transmission, and distribution planning, tariff & subsidy analysis, , and performance monitoring of sector entities.

National Electric Power Regulatory Authority (NEPRA): Acts as the independent regulator, responsible for tariff determination, licensing, enforcement of performance and service standards, and consumer protection in accordance with the NEPRA Act.

Distribution Companies (DISCOs): Responsible for electricity distribution to end-users, including network operation and maintenance, metering, billing, and revenue collection, as well as loss reduction and service quality improvements within their licensed areas.

2.2. Setting the Context

The Government of Pakistan recognizes electricity access as a critical enabler of socio-economic development, contributing to improved health outcomes, food security, education, access to information, and poverty alleviation, while supporting the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This commitment is reflected in the National Electricity Policy (NE-Policy) and the National Electricity Plan (NE-Plan), which collectively set the strategic direction for achieving universal, affordable, and reliable electricity access across the country.

To operationalize the target of 100% electrification by 2030, the Government has launched the Universal National Electrification (UNE) Program under the NE-Plan. Despite notable progress, electricity access remains uneven across provinces. While national access stands at approximately 87.3%, significant disparities persist, particularly in remote and sparsely populated areas where grid extension is economically challenging. Sindh, with an electrification rate of around 76% and Baluchistan with an electrification rate of 63% continues to host a substantial share of underserved settlements.

Electrification planning in Pakistan has been constrained by fragmented and inconsistent data across institutions, resulting in suboptimal investment decisions, infrastructure overlaps, weak progress monitoring, and limited visibility of underserved communities. At the same time, Pakistan’s power sector faces structural challenges, including surplus generation capacity of 5000 – 7000 MW, declining grid electricity sales, low system utilization, and financial stress in distribution companies. These dynamics necessitate a shift in electrification planning toward approaches that simultaneously expand access and improve system efficiency.

In response, Pakistan has developed a Central Electrification Registry (CER) to consolidate settlement-level electrification data and support evidence-based planning. To achieve the 100% electrification target by 2030, Government has mandated Ministry of Energy (Power Division) to develop a comprehensive roadmap for electrifying areas not covered under

existing projects, including identification of funding sources, eligibility criteria, and implementation timelines.

The objective of this report is to assess least-cost electrification pathways for Pakistan till 2030 and demonstrate the application of spatial modelling to support universal access goals while enhancing system efficiency.

The scope of the study is limited to one province—Sindh—serving as a pilot project for data-driven, spatially optimized electrification planning.

3. METHODOLOGY

This section is focused towards the modelling tools, process, data sets, assumptions and scenarios.

3.1. Modelling tools

The Open Source Spatial Electrification Tool (OnSSET) was the main modelling platform used in this study. OnSSET enables evaluation of alternative electrification pathways by simulating combinations of grid densification, grid extension, mini-grids, and standalone Solar Home Systems (SHS). Technology allocation is determined based on population distribution, electricity demand, resource availability, and proximity to existing infrastructure. Furthermore, QGIS was used for spatial data processing and visualization, while Python (Jupyter Notebook environment) supported data extraction and model execution.

Global Electrification Platform

3.2. Process Flow:

Data Acquisition

All required spatial and sectoral datasets for Pakistan were collected from national and open sources. These included:

- Power infrastructure (MV grid network)
- Population settlement clusters
- Administrative boundaries
- Road networks
- Night-time light intensity (proxy for electrification)
- Travel time data (accessibility)
- Solar resource potential
- Wind resource potential

These datasets provided the spatial foundation for electrification modelling.

Data Preparation in QGIS

All datasets were imported into QGIS and harmonized through:

- Reprojection into a common Coordinate Reference System (CRS)

- Cleaning of geometry and attribute inconsistencies
- Clipping to national boundaries
- Spatial alignment of raster and vector layers

This ensured consistency across layers before attribute extraction.

Attribute Extraction Using Python

Spatial attributes were extracted for each population settlement cluster using Python in a Jupyter Notebook environment:

- Anaconda was used to configure the Python environment
- GIS layers were overlaid with settlement points
- Key attributes (distance to grid, resource values, travel time, etc.) were assigned to each cluster

The extracted dataset was exported in CSV format.

CSV File Preparation

Using Python scripts:

- All extracted attributes were merged into a single structured CSV file
- Each row represented one settlement cluster
- Columns included demographic, infrastructure, and resource parameters required by OnSSET

This CSV file served as the primary input to the model.

Running OnSSET for Electrification Analysis

The OnSSET model was executed through Jupyter Notebook to:

- Calibrate current electrification levels to national statistics
- Compute technology-specific costs
- Assign the least-cost electrification technology per settlement
- Run multiple scenarios reflecting different policy and cost assumptions

Results Visualization in QGIS

Model outputs were re-imported into QGIS for spatial analysis:

- Scenario results were joined to settlement layers
- Thematic maps were produced showing technology allocation
- Spatial patterns of grid vs off-grid deployment were analyzed

3.3. Data Sources

A variety of open-access datasets were incorporated into the model, including:

- Solar potential: [Global Solar Atlas](#)
- Wind potential: [Global Wind Atlas](#)

- Administrative boundaries: [GADM](#)
- Population clusters: [Mendeley Dataset](#)
- Infrastructure and services: [Humanitarian Data Exchange](#)
- Power infrastructure: Ministry of Energy (Power Division) - Pakistan
- Road networks and features: [OpenStreetMap](#)

3.4. Assumptions

The modelling exercise applied a range of technical, demographic, and system-level assumptions for Pakistan, including:

Demographic Assumptions:

- **Administrative Area:** Administrative area of Sindh has been considered for the scope of analysis.
- **Start Year:** 2024
- **End Year:** 2030
- **Population context:** Population of approximately 55.6 million had been assumed for 2024 reaching to 60.7 million with CAGR of 1.5%.
- **Urbanization:** The Urbanization rate for 2024 was 54%, increasing to 56% in 2030 with remaining populations concentrated in dispersed and remote settlements

Technical Assumptions:

- **Target electrification rate:** 100% access by 2030
- **Demand targets:** Household electricity demand represented using a tier framework:
 - tier_1 = 20 kWh / HH
 - tier_2 = 73 kWh / HH
 - tier_3 = 365 kWh / HH
 - tier_4 = 1241 kWh / HH
 - tier_5 = 3000 kWh / HH
- **Grid System Parameters:** Following grid assumptions have been used:
 - Grid Generation Cost: 0.1128 \$/kWh
 - Estimated CAPEX of new power plant: 489 \$/kW
 - T&D Losses: 19%
 - HV_Line Cost: 125,000 \$/km
 - MV_Line Cost: 25,000 \$/km
 - LV_Line Cost: 2000 \$/km
 - HV-MV Transformer: 80,000 \$/unit
 - MV_LV Transformer: 8928 \$/unit

- **Solar Home System: 689 \$/kW**
- **Discount Rate: 10%**
- **Scenario Prioritization:**

Four prioritization options were built into the model, which can be used to decide which settlements to electrify first in order to reach the national electricity access target:

- Prioritization to electrify settlements with lowest investment cost per capita first.
- Prioritization to electrify the largest settlements first.
- Prioritization to electrify settlements with the shortest travel time to larger cities (>50,000 people first).
- Prioritization to electrify settlements closest to main roads first.

Base Case -Reference Scenario:

Following are the details of Reference case for Sindh where-in 76% of its total population is already electrified and the same has been shown in the figure below:

3.5. Scenarios

Following four (4) scenarios were simulated for the Sindh Province and out of that, the detailed results for two top down scenarios have been appended below:

#	Description	Demand*	Intensification Distance
S-1	Top Down High – Least Cost	High (U= 4, R = 3-2)	0 km
S-2	Top Down High – Forced grid	High (U= 4, R = 3-2)	15 km
S-3	Top Down Low – Least Cost	Low (U= 4, R = 2-1)	0 km
S-4	Top Down Low – Forced Grid	Low (U= 4, R = 2-1)	15 km

Scenario 1: Forced Grid (Strategic Demand Expansion)

This scenario is designed to address Pakistan's specific challenge of surplus grid capacity (estimated at 5,000–7,000 MW) by aggressively expanding the national grid.

- **Electrification Approach:** A combination of grid densification, extensive grid extension (modeled with a 15 km buffer), and limited use of Solar Home Systems (SHS) for the most remote areas.
- **Technology Mix:**
 - **Grid-Connected:** 56.58 million people (93% of the target).
 - **SHS-Based:** 4.16 million people (7% of the target).
- **Financial & Emissions Impact:**
 - **Total Investment:** USD 2,553 million. While higher, this represents only 2–5% of total power sector investments.
 - **Grid Sales:** Expected to generate an incremental 3–4 billion kWh/year in grid sales.
 - **Wholesale Tariffs:** Potential reduction of approximately 1 Rs/kWh due to better asset utilization.
 - **Emissions:** 296 tCO₂.
- **Strategic Rationale:**

It enables better utilization of existing generation capacity, improving the overall financial sustainability of the power sector.

	Population 2030 (M)	Investments M USD	Emissions 2030 (tCO2)
Grid densification	44.18	128	201
Grid Extension	12.40	2,178	95
SHS	4.16	246	0
Total	60.76	2,553	296

Scenario 2: Least-Cost (Minimum Capital Expenditure)

This scenario follows a purely economic path, selecting the technology with the lowest upfront cost for each settlement without considering broader grid utilization.

- **Electrification Approach:** Focuses on grid densification for existing areas and relies heavily on SHS for new access (modeled with a 0 km buffer for forced grid extension).
- **Technology Mix:**
 - **Grid-Connected:** 44.18 million people (73% of the target).
 - **SHS-Based:** 16.57 million people (27% of the target).

- **Financial & Emissions Impact:**

- **Total Investment:** USD 497 million.
- **Grid Sales:** Minimal impact on new grid-based revenue.
- **Emissions:** 201 tCO2.

- **Strategic Risk:** By diverting 27% of the population to off-grid solutions, this scenario limits future grid sales and worsens the risks associated with surplus capacity.

	Population 2030 (M)	Investments M USD	Emissions 2030 (tCO2)
Grid densification	44.18	128.48	201
SHS	16.57	368.62	0
Total	60.76	497.1	201

4. Results and Discussions

The results evaluate the transition from the current 87.3% access rate to universal 100% access for a projected population of 60.76 million.

4.1. Technology Mix and Population Reach

The modeling identifies two distinct pathways for achieving universal access, differing significantly in their reliance on the national grid versus standalone systems.

- **Scenario 1: Forced Grid (Grid-Heavy Pathway)**
 - **Grid Connection:** This scenario connects 56.58 million people (93%) to the national grid. This is achieved through both grid densification (connecting those near existing lines) and strategic grid extension.
 - **Off-Grid (SHS):** Only 4.16 million people (7%) in the most geographically challenging areas are relegated to Solar Home Systems (SHS).

- **Scenario 2: Least-Cost (Off-Grid Balanced Pathway)**
 - **Grid Connection:** Under a purely economic least-cost model, the grid-connected population drops to 44.18 million (73%).
 - **Off-Grid (SHS):** The reliance on SHS increases nearly fourfold to 16.57 million people (27%), as standalone solar becomes the "cheaper" upfront option for remote settlements.

Result Metric	Scenario 1: Forced Grid (Proposed)	Scenario 2: Least-Cost
Grid-Connected Population	56.58 million (93%)	44.18 million (73%)
SHS-Based Population	4.16 million (7%)	16.57 million (27%)
Total Investment Required	USD 2,553 million	USD 497 million
Carbon Emissions (2030)	296 tCO ₂	201 tCO ₂

4.2. Investment Requirements and Financial Analysis

The financial results highlight a trade-off between immediate capital savings and long-term sector health.

- **Capital Expenditure (CAPEX):**
 - **Scenario 1** requires an investment of USD 2,553 million. While substantially higher, it represents only 2-5% of Pakistan's total projected power sector investments for 10 years.
 - **Scenario 2** is significantly cheaper in the short term, requiring only USD 497.1 million.
- **Sector Sustainability:**
 - **Scenario 1** is expected to generate 3 to 4 billion kWh/year in incremental grid sales. By absorbing the current 5,000–7,000 MW surplus grid capacity, this scenario could reduce wholesale tariffs by approximately 1 Rs/kWh.
 - **Scenario 2** results in "minimal" incremental sales, which may worsen the financial burden of surplus capacity by diverting potential demand away from the grid.

4.3. Environmental Impact and Demand Profiles

The modeling accounted for varied consumption levels, from basic lighting to high-appliance households.

- **Emissions:** Scenario 1 results in higher emissions (296 tCO₂) compared to Scenario 2 (201 tCO₂) due to the higher utilization of the national grid, which includes thermal generation components.
- **Demand Tiers:** Results were modeled across different tiers, ensuring that "access" is not just a binary metric but reflects quality of service:
 - **Tier 2 - 4:** 73 kWh/household/year – 1,241 kWh/household/year

4.4. Analysis & Discussion

The choice of Scenario 1 over Scenario 2 is driven by the need to balance universal access with the financial health of the national utility.

- **Investment Feasibility:** Although the USD 2.55 billion investment for Scenario 1 is five times higher than Scenario 2, it represents only 2% to 5% of the total planned power sector investments for Pakistan. This makes the "Forced Grid" pathway a high-impact, relatively low-cost component of the broader national energy strategy.

- **The Surplus Capacity Paradox:** Unlike many developing nations that struggle with generation deficits, Pakistan faces a unique challenge of 5,000–7,000 MW in surplus grid capacity. This surplus creates a strategic imperative to "force" demand toward the national grid to ensure financial viability of power sector as a whole. Scenario 1 is designed to "force" grid expansion to tap into this existing supply, whereas a purely least-cost approach would leave this capacity underutilized.
- **The Cost of "Least-Cost":** A purely economic "Least-Cost" approach (Scenario 2) is actually more expensive for the power sector long-term. By diverting 27% of the population to standalone Solar Home Systems (SHS), it limits future grid sales and fails to address the "deemed capacity" payments associated with underutilized power plants.
- **Fiscal Sustainability:** Implementation of the proposed Forced Grid scenario is projected to generate 3 to 4 billion kWh/year in new grid sales.
- **Tariff Reduction:** Increased asset utilization under Scenario 1 is projected to reduce wholesale electricity tariffs by approximately 1 Rs/kWh, providing a broad economic benefit that Scenario 2 cannot offer.
- **Data Fragmentation as a Barrier:** The modeling process also highlighted that current data on electricity access is fragmented across multiple agencies and often outdated. This lack of visibility hinders efficient resource allocation and prevents accurate tracking of SDG 7 progress and highlights the importance of having a unified electrification framework for sustainable governance.
- **Environmental Trade-offs:** There is an environmental implication to the proposed strategy; Scenario 1 results in higher emissions (296 tCO₂) compared to the Least-Cost path (201 tCO₂). It is also highlighted that as grid demand is "forced" upward, the government is simultaneously prioritizing cleaning the generation mix to meet long-term climate goals which is expected to reach to above than 80% by 2035.
- **Risks of Not Choosing Scenario 1:** The analysis concludes that selecting the Least-Cost Scenario (Scenario 2) would be a strategic error for Pakistan. By diverting 27% of the population to standalone Solar Home Systems (SHS), the government would limit future on-grid demand, thereby worsening the financial risks associated with existing surplus capacity and "deemed capacity" payments

5. Conclusions & Recommendations

To achieve the 2030 target of 100% electrification, the following actions are recommended for Pakistan's energy planners:

5.1. 6.1 Strategic Implementation

- **Adopt Forced Grid Extension as a tool to increase on-grid sales:** Use grid expansion as a deliberate tool to spur on-grid electricity sales rather than just a social service.
- **Unified Policy Framework:** Establish a Central Electrification Registry (CER) to provide nationwide visibility and evidence-based decision-making for village electrification.
- **Integrate Frameworks:** Harmonize national, provincial, and private investments into a single electrification policy framework to prevent overlapping efforts.

5.2. 6.2 Tools and Analytical Capacity

- **Enhanced Modeling:** Position On-SSET as a continuous decision-support layer rather than a one-time standalone tool and integrate with short resolution tools like Micro-girds Py etc.

5.3. 7.0 Conclusion

The analysis concludes that Scenario 1: Forced Grid is the most viable pathway for Pakistan to achieve universal electricity access by 2030. While Scenario 2 offers the lowest upfront cost, it risks the long-term financial health of the power sector by underutilizing existing generation capacity. By investing USD 2,553 million in a grid-heavy approach, Pakistan can successfully bridge the access gap for 60.76 million people while simultaneously lowering electricity tariffs and improving the overall sustainability of its national energy infrastructure

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